

ZAMONAVIY DASTURLASH TILLARINI O'RGANISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy dasturlash tillarini o'rganishning ahamiyati haqida bo'lib, zamonaviy dasturlash tillarini o'rganish bo'yicha tasniflanadi va umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida 9-sinf o'quvchilari uchun Informatika va Axborot texnologiyalari fanidan o'rganiladigan Python dasturlash tili inkoniyatlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot, axborot texnologiyasi, dasturiy vosita, web ilova, algoritmi, dasturlash tillari, Python.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о важности изучения современных языков программирования, классифицируемых по современным языкам программирования, и Python для изучения в области компьютерных наук и информационных технологий для учащихся 9-х классов общеобразовательных средних школ.

Ключевые слова: информация, информационные технологии, программный инструмент, веб-приложение, алгоритм, языки программирования, Python.

Abstract. This article talks about the importance of learning modern programming languages classified by modern programming languages and Python for studying in the field of computer science and information technology for 9th grade general secondary school students.

Keywords: information, information technology, software tool, web application, algorithm, programming languages, Python.

Mamlakatda mustahkam ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotni ta'minlash axborot jamiyatini shakllantirish jarayonini amalga oshirish, axborot texnologiyalarini samarali joriy etish va foydalanishni talab etadi. Iqtisodiyotimizning barcha jabhalari, shu jumladan jamiyat hayotiga axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirib, uning bir necha barobar o'sishiga imkon yaratadi.

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Barcha turdagi axborot resurslari: dasturiy mahsulotlar, ma'lumotlar banki va bazasi, axborotlashtirish jarayonida ishlab chiqarilgan boshqa tovarlar axborot texnologiyalarining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Insoniyat taraqqiyot yutuqlaridan, yangi texnologiyalar va tayyor mahsulotlardan bu yangiliklar

qanday dunyoga kelganini o'ylab o'tirmasdan foydalanishga ko'nikkan. Bu mahsulotlardan biz foydalanishimiz uchun dasturchilar qanchalik uzoq va mashaqqatli yo'lni bosib o'tganini doim ham o'ylayvermaymiz. Axir mazkur yo'nalishlardagi mashaqqatli izlanishlarning poydevori ilmiy tadqiqotlar hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar aynan uning asosida quriladi. Shuning uchun ham axborotlashtirish darajasi rivojlangan davlatlar, yuqori texnologiyalar sohasidagi zamonaviy ishlab chiqaruvchi gigantlar ilmiy va amaliy tadqiqotlarga katta e'tibor qaratadi. Bisotida kuchli ilmiy jamoa va laboratoriyaga egalari bu tadqiqotlarga har yili milliardlab dollar mablag' Jumladan, mazkur sohaning normativ-huquqiy bazasi, moliyaviy-iqtisodiy, tashkiliy, kadrlar va boshqa jihatlarini takomillashtirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, ta'kidlash lozimki, mazkur yo'nalish bo'yicha ilmiy-texnik salohiyatni shakllantirish muhim faktorlardan biri hisoblanadi. Xorijning rivojlangan mamlakatlari tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, istalgan mamlakatning asosiy boyligi - ilmiy-texnik va intellektual salohiyatdan iborat. Bugungi kunda dunyo mamlakatlarida iqtisodiyotni taraqqiy toptirish yo'lida intellektual va ilmiy-texnik salohiyatning birlashtirilishi tendensiyasi kuzatilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi dasturiy mahsulotlar sanoatini rivojlantirish uchun yetarli darajada malakali ilmiy-texnik va texnologik ishlab chiqarish salohiyatiga ega. Mahalliy dasturiy mahsulotlar sanoati uchun, shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, mazkur segmentning o'ziga xosligi malakali mutaxassislariga katta talab borligi bilan farqlanadi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Bugungi kunda hukumatimiz tomonidan dasturiy mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish va milliy bozorini rivojlantirish bo'yicha qator choralar ko'rilmoqda.

Dasturlash tillari sohasida mutaxassislarni tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilyapti. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim, o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'lim tizimini tubdan isloh qilish va kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturini zamonaviy ilmiy tafakkur yutuqlariga, ilg'or tajribalarga tayangan holda, uzluksiz ta'lim tizimini barcha akademik liseylar va kasb-hunar kollejlarda ta'lim jarayonida zamonaviy dasturlash tillari bo'yicha bazaviy bilimlar beriladi.

Hozirgi dolzarb muammolardan biri dasturlash bo'yicha yuqori malakali, raqobatbardosh mutaxassis kadrlar tayyorlash, ularning kasbiy mahoratini takomillashtirishdan iborat.

MUHOKAMA

Zamonaviy dasturlash tillarini o'rgatuvchi o'quv materialini o'zlashtirish quyidagi darajalardan iborat:

- Boshlangich daraja - talabning eshitganlari ularga berilgan namunalarni, ko'rsatmalar algoritmlar asosida topshiriqlarni bajarish ko'nikmasini ifodalaydi.
- Algoritmik daraja - bilim va ko'nikmalar mazmunini tatbiq qila olish mahorati, berilgan algoritmlar bo'yicha topshiriqlarni mustaqil ravishda bajarish ko'nikmasini ifodalaydi.
- Evristik daraja - berilgan o'quv vazifalarini yechish uchun o'zgarishlar kiritish asosida yangi algoritmlar tuzish, o'quv muammosini hal etish uchun yangi axborotlarni mustaqil tarzda izlab topish malakasini aniqlaydi.
- Ijodiy daraja - avval o'rganilgan algoritmlardan butunlay farq qiluvchi, sifat jihatidan yangi algoritmlar tuza olish malakasi bilan ifodalanadi.

Zamonaviy dasturlash tillarini o'rganish bugungi kunning dolzarb masalalaridan biridir. Zamonaviy dasturlash tillari quidagicha tasniflanadi. Bugungi kunda umumta'lim maktablari 9-sinflar o'quvchilari uchun Informatika va Axborot texnologiyalarill fanidan Python dasturlash tili o'rgatilmoqda. Python dasturlash tili boshqa tillarga nisbatan o'rganish ancha oson va shu bilan birga imkoniyatlari boy bo'lgan til hisoblanadi. Ya'ni, til o'rganishni boshlovchilar uni osonlik bilan o'rganishlari mumkin, shu bilan bu til yordamida ancha-muncha jiddiy amaliy loyihalarni ham amalga oshirish mumkin.

XULOSA

Python haqida quyidagi uchta xulosaga kelish mumkin:

1. Python dasturlash tilining keng miqdarda qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan uch asosiy soha bor: veb-dasturlash (backend - vebserver uchun ilovalar yozish), sun'iy intellekt masalalari, kompyuterda foydalanuvchi juda ko'p marta bajaradigan mayda ishlar (elektron xatlarni jo'natish, fayllarni izlash va bosmalash, elektron jadvaldan biror-bir ma'lumotlarni ajratib olish va xakozolar).
2. Python o'rganish ancha oson bo'lgan dasturiy tildir. Agar tabiiy tillar bilan o'xshatish qiladigan bo'lsak, biror-bir tilda fikrni yetkazish uchun ma'lum vaqt so'zlarni, tilning grammatikasi o'rganish kerak bo'ladi. Qandaydir minimal bilim shakllangandan so'ng, asta -sekin inson o'z fikrini ifoda eta boshlaydi. Dasturlash tillari bilan ham holat xuddi shunday. Biror dasturlash tilida amaliy foyda keltiradigan dastur yozishni boshlash uchun ma'lum bilimlar majmuini egallash kerak, shundan so'nggina dasturlashni boshlash mumkin. Boshqa dasturlash tillaridan farqli ravishda, Python da amaliy ahamiyatga ega dasturlarni ishlab chiqishga ancha ertaroq, hali tilning katta qismini o'rganmasdan turib ham kirishish mumkin.

3. Python interpretatsiya qilinadigan dasturiy til. Dasturlash tillarini interpretatsiya qilinadigan va kompilyatsiya qilinadigan dasturlash tillariga bo'lishadi. Aniqroq aytganda, agar dasturlash tilidagi dasturni bajarish interpretatsiya orqali amalga oshirilsa, bunday tillar interpretatsiya qilanadigan til deyiladi. Agar dasturlash tilidagi dasturni bajarish uchun uni avval mashina tiliga o'tkazish talab qilinsa, bunday tillar kompilyatsiya qilinadigan ti llar deyiladi. Aslini olganda, kompyuter uchun yozilgan har qanday dastur interpretatsiya qilinadi. Chunki mashina kodlaridagi dastur kompyuterning miyasi bo'lgan protsessor tomonidan interpretatsiya qilinadi. Interpretatsiya qilinadigan tillarda yozilgan dasturlar uchun maxsus - interpretator dastur mavjud. Bu interpretator dastur kodlarini bajarilishini ta'minlab beradi.

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